
MOTIVATIONAL TECHNIQUES AS CORRELATES OF TEACHERS' JOB SATISFACTION IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract

The study examined the motivational techniques as correlates of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Three research questions guided the study and three null hypotheses were tested at 1.05 level of significance. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of the study comprised of 5147 teachers (795 males and 4352 females) in 263 public secondary schools in six Education Zones in Anambra State. The sample of 515 teachers (that is, 10% of the population) was used for the study. Proportional stratified and simple random sampling technique was used for the study. The instruments for data collection were researcher-structured questionnaire titled: Motivational Technique Questionnaire (MTQ) and Teachers' Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (TJSQ). The instruments were subjected to face validation by three experts. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha Coefficient method and the average coefficient for MTQ is .81 and 85 for TJSQ was obtained and was considered reliable and suitable for the study. The study used Pearson Product Moment Correlation and multiple-regression analysis for data analysis. The study showed that motivational techniques of teachers' fringe benefits, payment of salaries, professional development, involvement in decision-making, teamwork and work environment positively relate to teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study also revealed that there is a significant relationship between motivational techniques of teachers' fringe benefits, payment of salaries and professional development with teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommended among others that State government should review the current teachers' salaries and make it more attractive to motivate teachers, thereby directly enhancing their effectiveness and improving their satisfaction.

Keywords: Motivational Techniques, Teachers, Job Satisfaction, Fringe Benefits, Salaries, Professional Development

Introduction

The quest for survival and make ends meet and the desire to fulfill unending needs so as to live a comfortable life compels man to join an organization where he hopes to get the means of satisfying his insatiable needs. This, the organization does by boosting the morale of the employee and this is seen in the extent to which an individuals' need are met or satisfied and the extent to which the individuals perceives that satisfaction as stemming from his job situation.

Apparently in nature, teachers unlike other employees or workers tend to be committed to the jobs that they are satisfied with. For quality education to be achieved in a nation, one of the principal actors of learning (teachers) required to be satisfied with their job (Okafor & Enemuo, 2022). In recent time, education sector has witnessed increased interventions in teaches' factors in an attempt to improve teachers' quality for enhanced quality output and improved education. These efforts aimed at ensuring that the needs of teachers are met, having little or no attention to the motivational techniques that emphasis on the extrinsic and intrinsic needs of teachers towards their job satisfaction especially in public secondary schools in Anambra State. In support of this assertion, Batugal and Tindowen (2019) opined that there is a large vacuum that exists in terms of teachers' intrinsic needs as more incentives to teachers are extrinsic that are meant to boost teachers' morale and motivation.

The importance of staff in any educational system cannot be over-emphasized and for workers to perform their duties well, then working conditions should be favourable. Agbo (2018) maintained that employees and managers have to work in harmony, better cooperation and understanding in order to increase their productivity. It is therefore worth noting that every teaching institution needs not only the teaching staff, but also a motivated support staff to assist in running other services at the school (Muheeb, 2019). To ensure staff satisfaction and effective utilization of the available human resources for increased productivity, the work environment motivational level and conditions of service must be conducive and attractive.

When workers, teachers inclusive find everything satisfactory in their jobs, then there would be no cause for them not to perform or live up to the expectations of both the management and general public. The performance of a teacher in particular or any other worker lies on the degree of satisfaction he gets from the job or task that he performs. Since job satisfaction involves expectations compared with rewards, it relates to a psychological contract which an individual makes while joining an organization. The contract which the employees enter with the organisation stipulates each employee's psychological involvement with the organization.

In making the contract, the employees agree to give a certain amount of work and loyalty to the organization and in return seek economic rewards, security, and treatment as human beings among others. The honouring of the terms of the contract by both parties leads to job satisfaction. However, where and when an organization honour only part of the contract as the economic aspect, leaving the others, the workers would be dissatisfied. Where there is prolonged frustration, poor quality of work, lateness, absenteeism, quarrelling with colleagues, disputes with management among others is always the negative actions.

In the contemporary world today, attention is focused on education as an instrument for launching nations into the world of science and technology and with consequential hope of human advancement, in terms of living conditions and development of the environment. This is because in the life of any nation, education is the live-wire of its industries; it is the

foundation of moral regeneration and revival of its people. Thus, education is the bed-rock of any nation's development. It is that process that helps to develop the whole man physically, mentally, socially and technologically to enable him to function effectively in any environment in which he may find himself (FRN, 2014). Therefore, no nation can afford to pay lip service to the education of its people.

Education has been embraced by many nations as the greatest investment that can bring about civilization, modernization, development and socio-economic progress in the society. Education has also been considered as a necessary tool for human building and development. Ofojebe and Nnebedum (2016) opined that education is a vital tool for the inculcation of the right values and skills necessary for the development of individuals and the society at large. Thus, a nation that thinks lightly of education does so at its own peril. In this regard, Ogundele (2017) observed that no nation rises above the level of its education and no educational system outgrows the quality and status of its teachers: The important role education plays makes it necessary to understudy the standard and quality in secondary schools which cannot be completed without due inquest into the quality of school administrators and teachers.

The administration of secondary schools in Nigeria rests on the shoulders of the principal who is the leader, controller and custodian of both academic and extra-curricular activities of the school. According to Okebukola (2016), the principal is the chief executive of the school, who provides instructional leadership by coordinating curricular, co-curricular programmes and also responsible for the general administration of secondary schools. The principal is considered to be highest in hierarchy of authority in the secondary school charged with the tasks of planning, controlling and co-ordination of human, material, financial and time resources to foster the attainment of the school goals and objectives (Aku, 2017). To attain these objectives, the principal has to ensure that the teachers who are co-executioners of the schools' set objectives are duly motivated.

Motivation is one of the most vital concepts in human resource management and development. It is that desire or drive that an individual has to get work done (Uyanne et al, 2020). It is a critical aspect in functioning of every organization. It is capable of bringing forth the inner force to accomplish designed tasks effectively and productively. This is the focus of human resource management which every manager or leader is keenly interested in an effective organization. Motivation is very important because it explains why the employees do their work. The essential stimulus of work motivation is needs. Needs are the driving factors in developing work motivation while working in an organization. Thus, the objective of a person to work is similar with a teacher who is actually work to earn income and fulfill his/her needs, with hopes, desires and wishes that can be realized in his workplace (Adekanmbi & Ukpere, 2021).

Motivation can be classified as being intrinsic or extrinsic. Intrinsic motivation comes from within the job content which includes recognition, work itself, responsibility, advancement and growth. Onukwu and Okafor (2020) posited examples of intrinsic motivation to include acceptance, curiosity, honour, independence power and order. It is intrinsic motivation that makes teachers to respond to job challenges and work harder in order to prove their self-worth and integrity in the teaching profession. In the sense of this, teachers deliver their personal commitment and desire for personal accomplishment when intrinsically motivated. Extrinsic motivation on the other hand is derived from outside the job content which include, company policy and administration, supervision, relationship with supervisor, working conditions, salary (money), relationship with peers, personal life, relationship with

subordinates, status and security. Extrinsic motivation comes from outside the teacher and moves them to accomplish their tasks with a view to activating their rewards. In this sense, Izuchukwu (2020) expressed that extrinsic motivators such as good pay, retirement benefits, overtime allowances, good working conditions could spur or prompt the teacher to give in or deliver their best toward higher productivity. It then becomes the task of principals to discover the potential in each teacher, what motivate him/her and apply the appropriate strategy to see if their task performance will be enhanced.

To arrive at the point where the teachers are duly motivated, the principal has to be alive with basic motivational techniques. Motivational techniques involve various techniques that can be used to induce, encourage and stir employees in any organization to put in their very best in the discharge of their duties. Uyanne et al. (2020) affirmed that it encompasses so many things like the use of fringe benefits, incentives, style of management, working condition, wages and salaries, promotion and others to influence workers' productivity. Continuing, Uyanne et al. (2020) opined that in the developing nations like Africa, there is no greater motivation for workers like rewards usually in the form of wages and salaries. Toropova et al. (2021) were of the opinion that amongst other things, motivational techniques that could be employed by principals in motivating the teachers involves the use of fringe benefits, payment of salaries, conducive work environment, teachers' professional development, involvement in decision-making and teachers' teamwork among others.

Teachers' fringe benefits are additional compensation provided to teachers that is not directly related with their salary or wages for the performance of a specific service. Some fringe benefits such as social security and health insurance are required by law, while others are voluntarily provided by the employer. Examples of optional fringe benefits include free breakfast and lunch, gym membership, employee stock options, transportation benefits, retirement planning services, childcare, and education assistance, among others. Fringe benefits are a form of pay, often from employers to employees, and considered compensation for services beyond the employee's normal rate of pay. They can be made in the form of property, services, cash, or cash equivalents (Ibojo & Asabi, 2017). Cash equivalents are things that can be turned into cash fairly quickly, such as savings bonds. Teachers' fringe benefits in this study are regarded as the collection of various benefits provided by an employer, which are exempt from taxation as long as certain conditions are met. Thus, teachers' fringe benefits vary according to schools and can come in different forms like medical and dental insurance, use of a company car, housing allowance, educational assistance, vacation pay, sick pay, meals and employees' discounts among others.

Teachers' salary is a fixed amount of money agreed every year as pay for teachers, usually paid directly into his or her bank account every month. A salary is a form of payment from an employer to an employee, which might be specified in an employment contract. It is contrasted with piece wages, where each job, hour or other unit is paid separately, rather than on a periodic basis. From the point of view of running a business, salary could also be viewed as the cost of acquiring and retaining human resources for running operations, and is then termed personnel expense or salary expense. In accounting, salaries are recorded in payroll accounts. Salary is the regular payment by an employer to an employee for employment that is expressed either monthly or annually, but is paid most commonly on a monthly basis, especially to white collar workers, managers, directors and professionals (Izuchukwu, 2020). Salary is a fixed amount of money or compensation paid to an employee by an employer in return for work performed. Salary is commonly paid in fixed intervals, for example, monthly payments of one-twelfth of the annual salary. Salary is typically determined by comparing market pay rates for people performing similar work in similar industries in the same region.

Salary is also determined by leveling the pay rates and salary ranges established by an individual employer. Salary is also affected by the number of people available to perform the specific job in the employer's employment locale (Adekanmbi & Ukpere, 2021). Teachers' salary in this study is regarded as the reward for service and a source of livelihood for teachers. It is usually paid on a monthly basis. Regular payment of teachers' salary enhances their performance and boosts their morale.

Teachers' professional development is designed for the manpower development of the school system and the educational enterprise as a whole. If teachers are to perform their functions effectively and efficiently, it becomes imperative for them to require training in new skills and modern methodology. If a teacher is equipped on the job through development programmes, it will be reflected in the job performance. This made Onaolapo et al. (2020) to argue that teachers can only put in their best, if their professional needs to carry out their functions/duties are provided through staff development. This has made staff development become necessary especially in highly-populated schools where schools are short-staffed and some teachers are required to teach subjects outside their fields of specialization. In order to realize the overall aim of the school system, the teachers must be mobilized, directed, stimulated and motivated towards optimal performance of their duties. Teachers need to be motivated to partake in the seminars, workshops and conferences. Therefore, staff development is a dynamic (professional) function involving stimulating the teachers to improve the entire teaching-learning situation (Maclean, 2018). Thus, the ultimate aim of professional programmes for teachers is to ensure the effectiveness of teachers in the classroom and to increase students' achievement consequently (Onaolapo et al., 2020). Teachers' professional development in this study is regarded as the relevant courses and activities in which a serving teacher may participate to upgrade his professional knowledge, skills, and competence in the teaching profession. Therefore, it encompasses all forms of education and training given to a teacher who is already on the job of teaching and learning.

The truth of the matter is that the work of teaching and learning in secondary schools is anchored on the effectiveness of school principals and the teachers. It is only when the teachers are motivated that effective teaching and learning stands a chance of being implemented. This, of course, requires knowledge, skills and expertise on the part of the principals and teachers. However, taking a cursory look at the public secondary schools in Anambra State, the researcher observed with keen interest that the job satisfaction among the teachers basically leaves room for improvement. The researcher felt the need to inquire the extent these teachers are made beneficiaries of these motivational techniques by their principals. In particular, the researcher finds it interesting to find out if these motivational techniques affect the job satisfaction of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Over the past few years, the secondary school system in Anambra State has witnessed obvious loss of teachers' commitment to their professional responsibilities evidenced by poor attitude to duty, low performance and poor students' outcome despite huge government interventions on teachers' variables. From one of researcher's observation as a teacher in one of the public secondary school/in Anambra State, secondary school administration is characterized by obsolete and conventional methods of teacher management. The implication is teachers' lack of job satisfaction and non-commitment to duty, resulting in high rate of teachers' attrition. This is manifested in high percentage of teachers' absenteeism, truancy,

disloyalty, insensitive to students' discipline, non-chalant to school extra-curricular activities, voluntary turnover, and in fact, overall poor service delivery.

The unsatisfactory performance of some teachers often experienced in schools is always attributed to non-motivating fringe benefits, non-regular payment of teachers' salaries and inadequate teachers' professional development. In addition, inadequate use of motivational techniques by principals in schools could be the observed poor class attendance by teachers, in the sense that some of them look for other means of livelihood instead of relying only on teaching. Some qualified teachers are quitting teaching profession thereby giving room for the unqualified ones. Most of the teachers on ground are not given the opportunity for training and retraining so as to gain more knowledge and acquire basic teaching skills. In view of the above problems therefore, the researchers embarked upon this study to bridge the lacuna and determine motivational techniques as correlates of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine motivational techniques as correlates of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to determine the relationship existing between:

1. Fringe benefits and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Payment of salaries and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Professional development and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between fringe benefits and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the relationship between payment of salaries and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. What is the relationship between professional development and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between fringe benefits and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant relationship between payment of salaries and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. There is no significant relationship between professional development and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

The design of the study was correlational research design. The correlational research design, according to Stephen (2017), examined the degree, patterns and strength of relationship between two or more variables being studied rather than explore causal relationship between them. Therefore, the correlational research design becomes imperative since the study is multivariate analysis of the correlation between motivational techniques and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The area of the

study was Anambra State. The population of the study comprised 5,147 teachers (795 males and 4,352 females) in 263 public secondary schools in six education zone in Anambra State. The sample size of the study comprised 515 teachers (that is, 10% of the population) drawn using proportionate stratified and simple random sampling technique.

The instruments for data collection were researchers-structured questionnaire titled “Motivational Technique Questionnaire (MTQ) and Teachers’ Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (TJSQ). The face and construct validation of the instruments were determined. The face validation was established by three experts (two in the area of Educational Management and one in the area of Measurement and Evaluating) all from the Department of Educational Foundations in the Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus. Their comments were considered and used in modifying the instruments for final data collection. On the other hand, the construct validation was determined using Principle Component Analysis approach with Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) as a measure of sampling adequacy to construct the Principle Component Analysis. The reliability of the instruments was established using Cronbach alpha method. The coefficient obtained were 0.78, 0.81 and 0.82 for Clusters A-C of MTQ and 0.85 for TJSQ. The researcher visited the selected schools with the aid of three research assistants who were briefed on how to administer and retrieve the instruments from the sampled respondents. Out of 515 copies of the instruments administered, 492 (96%) of the instruments were correctly completed and returned, while 23(4%) were either misplaced or not correctly filled. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses. For the research, + sign = Positive Relationship, while – Sign = Negative Relationship. For hypotheses, when, sig. (2-tailed) < .05: Reject H₀ and Accept H₁, while sig. (2-tailed) > .05: Accept H₀ and Reject H₁.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between fringe benefits and teachers’ job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Relationship Between Fringe Benefits and Teachers’ Job Satisfaction in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Fringe Benefits	Teachers’ Job Satisfaction
Fringe Benefits	Pearson Correlation (r)	1	.327**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	492	429
Teachers’ Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation (r)	.327**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	492	492

**Significant at $p < 0.05$; $r^2 = 0.251482$; % = 25.1

The summary result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient in Table 1 showed the relationship between fringe benefits and teachers’ job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria with: $r = .327$, $r^2 = 0.251482$, percent (%) = 25.1 and $N = 492$. This revealed a positive correlation coefficient value of .327 which indicated that there is a positive relationship existing between fringe benefits and teachers’ job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Thus, the study showed that there is a positive relationship between fringe benefits and teachers’ job

satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The r^2 of 0.251482 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable which implies that 25.1% of the variations in fringe benefits were accounted for by the variations in teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between payment of salaries and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Relationship Between Payment of Salaries and Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Payment of Salaries	Teachers' Job Satisfaction
Payment of Salaries	Pearson Correlation (r)	1	.622**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	492	429
Teachers' Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation (r)	.622**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	492	492

**Significant at $p < 0.05$; $r^2 = 0.447065$; % = 44.7

The summary result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient in Table 2 showed the relationship between payment of salaries and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria with: $r = .622$ $r^2 = 0.447065$, percent (%) = 44.7 and $N = 492$. This revealed a positive correlation coefficient value of .622 which indicated that there is a positive relationship existing between payment of salaries and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Thus, the study showed that there is a positive relationship between payment of salaries and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The r^2 of 0.447065 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable which implies that 44.7% of the variations in payment of salaries were accounted for by the variations in teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between professional development and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 3: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Relationship Between Professional Development and Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Professional Development	Teachers' Job Satisfaction
Professional Development	Pearson Correlation (r)	1	.501**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	492	429
Teachers' Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation (r)	.501**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	492	492

**Significant at $p < 0.05$; $r^2 = 0.350371$; % = 35.0

The summary result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient in Table 1 showed the relationship between professional development and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria with: $r = .501$, $r^2 = 0.350371$, percent (%) = 35.0 and $N = 492$. This revealed a positive correlation coefficient value of .501 which indicated that there is a positive relationship existing between professional development and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Thus, the study showed that there is a positive relationship between professional development and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The r^2 of 0.2=350371 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable which implies that 35.0% of the variations in professional development were accounted for by the variations in teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between fringe benefits and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Test of Significant Relationship Between Fringe Benefits and Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Fringe Benefits	Teachers' Job Satisfaction
Fringe Benefits	Pearson Correlation (r)	1	.327**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	492	429
Teachers' Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation (r)	.327**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	492	492

**Significant at $p < 0.05$; $r^2 = 0.251482$; % = 25.1

The summary result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient in Table 4 showed the relationship between fringe benefits and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria with p-value = .000. Since the p-value (.000) is less than .05, the study rejected the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between fringe benefits and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that there is significant relationship between fringe benefits and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between payment of salaries and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 5: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Test of Significant Relationship Between Payment of Salaries and Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Payment of Salaries	Teachers' Job Satisfaction
Payment of Salaries	Pearson Correlation (r)	1	.622**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	492	429
Teachers' Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation (r)	.622**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	492	492

**Significant at $p < 0.05$; $r^2 = 0.447065$; % = 44.7

The summary result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient in Table 5 showed the relationship between payment of salaries and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria with p-value = .000. Since the p-value (.000) is less than .05, the study rejected the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between payment of salaries and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that there is significant relationship between payment of salaries and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between professional development and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Test of Significant Relationship Between Professional Development and Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Professional Development	Teachers' Job Satisfaction
Professional Development	Pearson Correlation (r)	1	.501**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	492	429
Teachers' Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation (r)	.501**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	492	492

**Significant at $p < 0.05$; $r^2 = 0.350371$; % = 35.0

The summary result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient in Table 6 showed the relationship between professional development and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria with p-value = .000. Since the p-value (.000) is less than .05, the study rejected the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between professional development and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that there is significant relationship between professional development and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion

Findings on the relationship between fringe benefits and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State showed that fringe benefits has a positive and significant relationship with teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The findings is as a result of teachers accepting that their satisfaction on the job emanate from the provision of free transportation, school payment of hospital bills, provision of scholarship to teachers' children, provision of loan, provision of wardrobe allowance, availability of free accommodations, provision of free drugs, duty tour allowances paid, welfare packages given and amenities such as water and light provided for teachers that enhance their job in the school. Thus, providing fringe benefits to teachers get them satisfied with their job. The findings are in line with the findings of Ibojo and Asabi (2017) and Ohide and Mbogo (2018). They observed that fringe benefits have a positive and significant relationship with teachers' job satisfaction. The similarity of the findings is as a result of using similar fringe benefits such as school payment of hospital bills, provision of loan to teachers, availability of free accommodations and provision of free transportation among others. The study also showed that fringe benefits account for 25.1% of the variations in

teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The finding is in agreement with the studies of Toropova et al (2021) whose findings indicated that a unit change in fringe benefits causes a proportional unit change in teachers' job satisfaction. The similarity in the findings could be as a result of the use of fringe benefits as a support services provided by the school authorities to the teachers in order to motivate them and boost their morale for better performance and achievement in schools.

Findings on the relationship between payment of salaries and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State showed that payment of salaries has a positive and significant relationship with teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The result of the study raised from the fact that teachers agreed that payment of salaries give them the zeal to work, save them the embarrassment of being a debtor thereby motivate them to work, boost their morale toward their work, lead to positive teaching and learning outcomes, induce them to be committed to their work, enable them to settle their outstanding debts in order to focus on their duties, provide them with cash thereby facilitating their coming to school early, make them to energize the behaviour of students, improves their standard of living, and make them to sustain students' interest for a longer activity in the classroom. The finding of the study is in consonance with Adekanmi and Ukpere (2021) who disclosed that payment of salaries and teachers' job satisfaction has a positive and significant relationship. Thus, increase or prompt or regular payment of salaries leads to higher job satisfaction of teachers in schools (Ofojebe & Nnebedum, 2016). The studies along the present study advocated that payment of salaries do not only contribute to teachers' effectiveness but also to their job satisfaction. The similarities observed in the studies could be as a result of teachers being satisfied with the frequencies and mode of payment of salaries in various schools. Again, findings from Obiora (2019) and Grub (2020) indicated that payment of salaries has a positive and significant relationship with teachers' job satisfaction. From the study perspective, payment of salaries account for 44.7% of the variations in teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State. These similarities in various studies could be that payment of salaries is the most vital motivational technique that helps to promote and improve teachers' job satisfaction in schools.

Findings on the relationship between professional development and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State showed that professional development has a positive and significant with teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The result of the study could be attributed to the fact that teachers are encouraged to go for conferences, newly recruited staff are oriented, the school organizes symposium for teachers, the school principals encourages experienced staff to mentor less experienced staff, staff are encouraged to go for workshops for better service delivery, in-service training creates the chance for teachers to get feedback about their instruction, teachers are provided with opportunities to learn and use the skills learned to generate new knowledge, attending training is a part of a continuous process to build on the teacher's current knowledge and sponsoring teachers to capacity building workshop increases teachers' job satisfaction. This result is in agreement with the finding of Ogbu (2017) and Onaolapo *et al* (2020). Ogbu (2017) found a positive and significant relationship between in-service and job satisfaction in schools. They argued that teachers engage themselves in seminar and conference training in order to develop their teaching skills and knowledge, Onaolapo *et al* (2020) disclosed that professional development of teachers have a positive and significant relationship with job satisfaction. On the other hand, the study indicated that the positive and significant relationship between professional development and teachers' job satisfaction in schools could be attributed to teachers being better at planning their time and staying

organized with the teaching profession. This ultimately makes teachers more efficient and gives them extra time to focus on students rather than the paperwork. This finding is in line with finding of Maclean (2018) who indicated that teachers who attend in-service training give them the edge over their colleagues as it positively and significantly contributes to teachers' job satisfaction. In the words of Tijani (2020), the positive and significant correlation between professional development of teachers in their job satisfaction is as a result of teachers attending in-service training, seminar and conferences. The fact remains that the positive and significant relationship observed by the previous and present studies could be proved that professional development boosts up the efficiency and effectiveness of teachers and develops a sense of perfect behaviour in their working strategies. Professional development acts as a catalyst for a teachers' effectiveness. Onaolapo et al (2020) revealed that it is also a way of updating teachers' skills and knowledge for improving teaching and learning which lead to better job performance. Thus, teachers' professional development is important for teachers to face new challenges and changes in the education world.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it is concluded that motivational techniques were positive and significant correlates of teachers'-job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The motivational techniques of teachers' fringe benefits, payment of salaries and professional development. As it is clear that motivation in any work is the boost factor for increment of achievements and productive output, motivational techniques becomes an indispensable factor for motivating teachers to be satisfied and be committed to their job

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. School authorities should set up policies and programmes that will improve the working conditions of teachers, likewise creating room for adequate teachers' support services and empowerment in form of fringe benefits.
2. State government should review the current teachers' salaries and make it more attractive to motivate teachers, thereby directly enhancing their effectiveness and improving their satisfaction.
3. Educational planners should create awareness to school principal and teachers by organizing conferences, seminars and workshop to address teachers' perception of school climate as relates to their job performance. With this information, it would encourage principals to create comfortable atmosphere that will enhance teachers' job satisfaction.

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